

Unlocking teachers' organizational citizenship behavior: exploring compensation in transmitting visionary leadership

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ABSTRACT

For both organizational and personal life, especially for teachers in the context of schools, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), is essential. Thus, this study investigates and creates a novel empirical model of the mediation mechanism of compensation on the relationship between visionary leadership and teachers' OCB. For this study, 230 private junior high school teachers in three Indonesian provinces Jakarta, West Java, and Banten were given Likert scale questionnaires. With survey methods and analyses by structural equation modeling (SEM) found a significant impact of visionary leadership and compensation on OCB, the substantial influence of visionary leadership on compensation, and the significant effect of visionary leadership on OCB through compensation. This evidence supports a novelty about visionary leadership, through compensation, affects teachers' OCB. It is in line with and confirms the results of previous research as the basis of this research and, at the same time, negates the conflicting results of previous research. Under these circumstances, the novel model offers a theoretical and practical contribution that necessitates thorough and critical debate prior to adoption, adaptation, or modification as a model for enhancing teachers' OCB through visionary leadership backed by compensation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB's) crucial role in both personal and organizational life makes it a subject of constant interest. In organizational scope, OCB contributes to organizational performance and competitiveness [1], [2]. Meanwhile, in a personal area, OCB affects work performance [3], which includes task performance [4] and contextual performance [5]. In the school context, OCB is also important for the lives of individuals and organizations, including teachers. When Indonesian schools emerge in a crisis: 50% of students fail to fulfill basic literacy competencies, and 67% fail to fulfill numeracy literacy competencies (2021), teacher OCB is very important. Additional issues that can be mitigated by OCB, include learning activities before and after COVID-19, or adjusting to the adoption of the independent curriculum, which is a very taxing process mentally and physically.

Beyond the call of duty, OCB demonstrated voluntary extra-role behavior that enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization in achieving its objectives. It is considered extra-task behavior that is not regulated in the organization's compensation system [6]. Moreover, OCB refers to unpaid conduct that extends beyond official work responsibilities and is necessary to support an organization's continued existence [7]. It is the expression of actions made by staff members that, while not necessary for their current

position or duty, support the operations and expansion of the company [8]. Individual behavior that voluntarily and openly promotes more effective and efficient organizational activities is referred to as OCB [9]. OCB is particularly significant in a time of unpredictability because teachers' willingness to participate, independent of official job responsibilities, frees up limited resources, aids in activity coordination, and improves group cohesion. Schools can recover from crises more quickly if they exhibit these pro-social practices, which can make them more resilient and responsive [10].

There are five indications in the OCB. First, altruism is the act of providing assistance to others, such as coworkers who are experiencing difficulties finishing tasks or resolving personal issues. Secondly, conscientiousness is related to the knowledge to do good that goes beyond the organization's needs. Third, sportsmanship shows that one is accepting of subpar organizational circumstances. Fourth, courtesy indicates a desire to reduce interpersonal conflict by making every effort to promote social relationships with others. Fifth, civic virtue is the ability to act in a way that promotes organizational survival [11]. Schools genuinely need these OCB indicators to handle emergency or unusual situations.

Researchers demonstrated that OCB is affected by visionary leadership [12], [13] and compensation [14], [15]. Other studies indicated that leadership affects compensation [16]. Additionally, visionary leadership is related to salary as a job satisfaction parameter [17]. However, other prior studies indicated contrasting results. For instance, leadership does not influence OCB [18]. Besides, compensation does not contribute to OCB [19]. These inconsistent research results give rise to research gaps that must be clarified scientifically. Based on the urgency, this research question is: How does visionary leadership impact teachers' OCB, does compensation affect teachers' OCB, and does compensation mediate the effect of visionary leadership on teachers' OCB? Therefore, this research aims to provide a solution for it by exploring the effect of visionary leadership on teachers' OCB, both directly and indirectly, through compensation.

With good empirical justification, visionary leadership is growing in popularity. Previous research proved that visionary leadership influences various domains, including creativity, and leads followers to realize a shared vision [20]–[22]. Furthermore, studies have shown that it boosts leadership [23], enhances followers' dedication [24], and improves work outcomes [25], including performance [26]. Visionary leadership also determines change management techniques and enterprise development [27]–[29]. A leader who practices visionary leadership can persuade others or subordinates to be engaged in developing and communicating an appealing, practical, and convincing vision that will enhance the state of affairs as it stands [30]. It involves relentlessly pursuing a goal of improving things [31]. Thus, visionary leadership is defined as a leader's ability to motivate subordinates to accomplish organizational objectives in order to come up with novel ideas or approaches to problem-solving [32]. Aiming for the long term rather than the quick fix is a hallmark of visionary leadership. In contrast to stability and control, they are more interested in innovation and change. They have essentially altered their establishments [33]. Visionary leadership involves motivating, influencing, and optimally involving subordinates in order to conceive, introduce, and realize the organization's vision [13]. A visionary leader is someone who can create a compelling vision for the future of his organization, win over his team's devotion to it, and implement that vision by implementing the required organizational adjustments [34]. Visionary leaders have several distinctive characteristics that can be used as measurement parameters, namely: high standards and ideas, clarifying direction and goals, inspiring enthusiasm and commitment, having effective communication, reflecting the competence and uniqueness of the organization, and having a solid willingness to realize goals [35]. These kinds of leaders have a great tendency to encourage their subordinates' OCB growth. For instance, they act responsibly to ensure the existence of the organization and are conscious of doing good or going above and beyond what is expected of them. Principals that exhibit strong, visionary leadership in the school setting have a tendency to encourage teachers' OCB. According to earlier research, visionary leadership affects OCB [13], [36], [37]. It can therefore support the first hypothesis: Visionary leadership has positively affected OCB (H_1).

Compensation has always been a critical issue that has attracted the attention of practitioners and researchers for several reasons. First, at the individual level, compensation has been proven to have a significant effect on increasing employee productivity [38]–[40] and performance [41], [42]. Second, at the organizational level, compensation can encourage improvements in organizational performance [43], [44]. This empirical finding demonstrates the significant impact that compensation has on the lives of both individuals and companies (workers). From a conceptual standpoint, compensation encompasses all monetary disbursements as well as any assets or commodities that are valued at money and utilized to compensate workers [45]. Compensation can alternatively be defined as an organization's promise to pay an employee everything they want, value, and are prepared to give in exchange or as their entire salary and benefits [46]. Compensation includes intrinsic and extrinsic compensation. Extrinsic compensation includes monetary compensation, representing core compensation, such as salary, seniority, service, incentive, knowledge plans, and skills wages and benefits. On the other hand, sentiments of proficiency, achievement, accountability, and personal development provide intrinsic compensation. The psychological perspectives that arise from people carrying

out their jobs are also reflected in intrinsic compensation [47]. As a result, compensation comprises both material benefits that the company pays its employees as well as intangible benefits like chances for growth and advancement, social standing, and professional accomplishments [48], [49]. Compensation can be measured through several indicators, such as salary, fringe benefits, incentives, protection programs, feelings of competence, accomplishment, responsibility, and personal growth [47], [50]. Scholars claim that compensation affects OCB [14], [15], [51]–[55]. It addressed that compensation is a crucial antecedent for OCB. Accordingly, it can formulate the second hypothesis: compensation positively affects OCB (H_2).

Compensation not only influences OCB but also potentially to be influenced by visionary leadership. A study found that leadership influences compensation [16]. Another study indicated that visionary leadership impacts salary as an indicator of job satisfaction [17]. It shows that there is a possibility that visionary leadership links to compensation. As an illustration, when a school principal has high standards, compensation can be used to share those standards as a strategy to inspire and build teacher commitment to realizing school goals. So, it stands to reason that visionary leadership has an impact on compensation. Consequently, it is able to put out the third hypothesis: Visionary leadership has positively affected compensation (H_3).

Several studies above show that compensation can mediate the influence of visionary leadership on OCB. It can happen because apart from being influenced by visionary leadership [16], [17], compensation also has a significant positive impact on OCB [51]–[55]. However, research that specifically investigates how visionary leadership affects OCB via compensation still needs to be found. This condition opens opportunities for the discovery of novelty, so it is crucial to investigate. Based on previous studies and the explanation above, we propose the following hypothesis: Visionary leadership has a positive effect on OCB through compensation (H_4).

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Participants

There were 230 participants in the research (sample). This is in line with the suggested minimum sample size of 100–300 for structural equation modelling (SEM) parameter estimates [56]. They work as private junior high school teachers in Jakarta, West Java, and Banten, three Indonesian provinces. They were selected through accidental sampling in accordance with their availability and willingness to complete the questionnaire in its entirety without being paid for the research [57] by endorsing the information supplied for research data and scholarly publications. In detail, female respondents make up 54.78% of the sample, with 36.52% of respondents being between 26 and 35 years old, 83.48% having a bachelor's degree, 74.35% being married, and 34.78% having fewer than five years of experience.

2.2. Procedure and materials

This study used a survey method along with a quantitative approach. Five options were included in the questionnaire, which used a Likert scale to collect data: strongly disagree/never (score = 1), disagree/rarely (score = 2), neutral/sometimes (score = 3), agree/often (score = 4), and strongly agree/always (score = 5). Google Forms, which may be shared via email and the WhatsApp app, was used to conduct the online survey. Researchers created the questionnaire using the experts' theoretical dimensions or indications as a guide from the experts. The visionary leadership indicators were: high standards and ideas (HSI), clarifying direction and goals (CGD), inspiring spirit and commitment (ISC), having effective communication (HEC), reflecting competencies and organizational uniqueness (RCOU), and having a strong desire to pursue goals (SDPG) [35]; for compensation: pay, fringe benefits (FB), incentive (Inc), protection programs (PP), feelings of competence (FC), accomplishment (Acc), responsibility (Res), and personal growth (PG) [47], [50]; and for OCB: altruism (Alt), conscientiousness (Con), sportsmanship (Spo), courtesy (Cou), and civic virtue (CV) [11]. Twelve items make up the visionary leadership, and their corrected item-total correlation coefficient (CI-TCC) ranges from 0.518 to 0.886, with an alpha coefficient (AC) of 0.943. The compensation consists of ten items with CI-TCC between 0.469 and 0.812, with an AC of 0.914. There are 10 items in the OCB, and their AC is 0.872 and their CI-TCC ranges from .437 to .829. It is valid and reliable as a research instrument because every item has a CI-TCC of >0.361 and every variable has an AC of >0.70 [56]. Additionally, a matching approach is used to control confounding variables. It offers many customization options, which allow a researcher to incorporate substantive knowledge and carefully manage bias/variance trade-offs in estimating the effects of nonrandomized exposures [58]. In this study, confounding variables were controlled by gender, age, education, marital status, and length of work.

Finally, a common method bias (CMB) analysis was carried out to control data bias. Many scholars think that when cross-sectional survey studies use self-report questionnaires like the one used in this study, common method bias (CMB), one source of measurement error [59]. The difference between the reported relationship and the actual correlation between variables as CMB is generated by the common method variance

(CMV). It could lead to an increase in the apparent correlation relative to the genuine correlation [60]. CMV thus jeopardizes the reliability and consistency of study results. Fuller *et al.* [61] suggest applying statistical methods, such as the correlation matrix methodology and Harman's single-factor test, to reduce and regulate CMV. The findings of Harman's single-factor test show that the correlation coefficient between the construct (variable) is less than 0.90 and that the total variance extracted by one factor is 49.12%, which is less than the suggested threshold of 50%. It implies that there is no CMV (CMB) in the study's data [62]–[64].

2.3. Data analysis

Structural equation modelling (SEM), together with correlational and descriptive statistics, was used to analyze the data. A student's t-test was used to determine the route coefficients correlation's direct and indirect significance. SPSS version 22 was used for the CMB, descriptive, and correlation analyses, while LISREL version 8.80 was used for the SEM analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Descriptive and correlation analysis

The findings of the descriptive and correlation studies performed with SPSS, the mean values, which normally fall between 3.56 and 8.92, are larger than the standard deviation (SD) values, which range from 0.650 to 2.056. Consequently, it offers a respectable synopsis of the information and begs for more research. All constructs (variables) collectively show significant correlation research results between indicators at $p < 0.01$, with a correlation coefficient value range of 0.13 – 0.79. It illustrates the mutual dependence between every indication and all others. But since the correlation coefficient that was found is less than 0.8, there is no indication of multicollinearity in this relationship.

3.2. Confirmatory factor analysis

Table 1 displays the measurement model estimate derived from confirmatory factor analysis. All indicators and items have factor loading values of ≥ 0.50 , demonstrating validity. Thus, variables are involved. Concurrently, the construct reliability (CR), variance extracted (VE), and alpha (α) values were used to determine reliability. All variables have strong reliability and adequate convergence, with CR and α values greater than 0.70 and VE values greater than 0.50 [56].

Table 1. Result of the measurement model

Constructs	Indicators	Factor loading	CR	VE	α
Visionary leadership (X)	HSI	0.85	0.940	0.723	0.943
	CGD	0.92			
	ISC	0.89			
	HEC	0.78			
	RCOU	0.88			
	SDPG	0.77			
Compensation (Y ₁)	FB	0.74	0.917	0.613	0.914
	Inc	0.78			
	PP	0.84			
	FC	0.84			
	Acc	0.80			
	Res	0.75			
OCB (Y ₂)	PG	0.72	0.814	0.575	0.828
	Alt	0.56			
	Con	0.80			
	Spo	0.85			
	Cou	0.58			
	CV	0.60			

3.3. Goodness of fit

The goodness of fit (GOF) statistical analysis results showed that out of the eleven measurements of the criterion, eight had GOF indices (GFI, NFI, NNFGI, AGFI, CFI, Normed Chi-Square, PNFI); whereas the other three (chi-square, sig., probability, and RMSEA value) did not. Hair *et al.* [56] claim that the chi square test needs to be used in conjunction with another testing technique because it is extremely sensitive to big sample sizes (>200). Since 230 teachers participated in this study, the chi-square test and sig. probability values were deemed invalid. However, since the other eight criteria that were examined had appropriate standards, it was still deemed legitimate.

3.4. Hypothesis testing

The result from the hypothesis tests is visualized in Figures 1 and 2, and summarized in Table 2. All hypotheses were supported (significant) with t -value $>$ t -table at $\alpha=0.01$. In detail, visionary leadership significantly affects OCB ($\gamma=0.24$, $p<0.01$), compensation significantly impacts OCB ($\beta=0.26$, $p<0.01$), visionary leadership significantly influences compensation ($\gamma=0.70$, $p<0.01$), and visionary leadership has a significant effect on OCB mediated by compensation ($\beta=0.19$, $p<0.01$). The effect of visionary leadership on compensation is greater than OCB. It indicated that visionary leadership practices are more effective in increasing compensation than OCB.

Figure 1. Standardized structural model

Figure 2. T-value structural model

Table 2. Hypothesis testing result

Hypothesis	γ/β	T-value	Decision
H ₁ : Visionary leadership (X) and OCB (Y ₂)	0.24**	2.34	Supported
H ₂ : Compensation (Y ₁) and OCB (Y ₂)	0.26**	2.49	Supported
H ₃ : Visionary leadership (X) and compensation (Y ₁)	0.70**	9.40	Supported
H ₄ : Visionary leadership (X) on OCB (Y ₂) mediated by compensation (Y ₁)	0.19**	2.46	Supported

** $p < 0.01$

3.5. Discussion

The overall findings of this study indicate that OCB is positively impacted by visionary leadership and compensation, visionary leadership positively influences compensation, and compensation mediates the effect of leadership on OCB. Specifically, visionary leadership affects OCB, indicating that it is a significant predictor of OCB. The positive outcome suggests that increasing the principal's use of visionary leadership can stimulate higher levels of OCB among teachers. It demonstrates that principals of schools that actively practice visionary leadership can eventually promote an increase in the OCB of teachers. A school principal with high standards, inspirational, and communicative will motivate teachers to strive to exceed what is expected of them and take responsibility for the success of the school. This finding is consistent with other studies that found a positive relationship between visionary leadership and OCB [13], [36], [37] and refutes relevant research findings that leadership had no discernible effect on OCB [18].

This study also reveals that compensation has an effect on OCB. It confirms that compensation is a crucial determinant of teacher OCB. The effect is positive, indicating that improving compensation can stimulate an increase in OCB among teachers. These findings also show that although OCB is an extra-role and prosocial behavior that has a voluntary nuance, it actually has an intersection with the compensation received by teachers, such as salary, fringe benefits, incentives, protection programs, feelings of competence, accomplishment, responsibility, and personal growth [47], [50]. It is an interesting and valuable lesson for all groups that prosocial behavior such as altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy, and civic virtue as manifestations of OCB can be increased through compensation. This finding is not only in line with and confirms the results of previous research that compensation influences OCB [14], [15], [54], [55] but also refutes the results of the investigation that proved that compensation does not significantly affect OCB [19].

In addition, this study also found other empirical facts that visionary leadership has a significant effect on compensation. It shows that visionary leadership is a strategic antecedent for compensation. The influence is positive so that it has the consequence that when the implementation of visionary leadership is intensified, it can have implications for improving compensation. These findings provide a factual understanding that high standards, as one of the important pillars of visionary leadership, also extend to high compensation standards. This finding is in line with and strengthens previous studies that leadership influences compensation [16], [17].

Finally, this research finds new empirical facts that visionary leadership positively affects teachers' OCB via compensation. It suggests the crucial mediating role of compensation in linking visionary leadership with teachers' OCB. It sends a message that raising teacher OCB based on visionary leadership principles will work best when accompanied by appropriate compensation. These findings not only confirm previous studies as a basis for building theoretical models and hypotheses [12]-[17], [36], [37], [51]-[55] and negate prior studies contradictory [18], [19], but also promote a new empirical model regarding the influence of visionary leadership on teachers' OCB through compensation. This model can provide theoretical contributions to the study of OCB from the perspective of visionary leadership with compensation mediation, especially in the study areas of leadership and organizational behavior, HRM, educational management, and organizational psychology. Additionally, this model also has the potential to provide practical contributions to leadership practices in school organizations, especially in order to increase teachers' compensation and OCB.

4. CONCLUSION

Organizations and individuals need OCB to anticipate various actual needs and respond to future challenges. Therefore, this study investigates teachers' OCB based on visionary leadership and compensation perspective. The results show that visionary leadership and compensation impact OCB, visionary leadership affects compensation, and visionary leadership influences OCB through compensation. This evidence supports a novelty about how visionary leadership affects teachers' OCB through compensation. It is not only in line with and confirms the results of previous research as the basis of this research and negate prior studies contradictory but also negates the conflicting results of previous research. Under these circumstances, the novel model offers a theoretical and practical contribution that necessitates thorough and critical debate prior to adoption, adaptation, or modification as a model for enhancing teachers' OCB through visionary leadership backed by compensation with considered several of this study's limitations, such as only involves a single data

source (teacher) and accommodate several theoretical dimensions/indicators. Future research consistent with the results of this study should address these limitations.

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